

Supplementary Information

Controlling crystal morphology of anisotropic zeolites with elemental composition

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Figure S1: Schematic representation of the **UTL** zeolite crystal with projections along the a-, b- and c-axis and SEM image of the **UTL** (Si/Ge = 5.26) sample with the highlighted crystallographic plane angle corresponding to the geometry of the **UTL** topology

Figure S2: Argon adsorption-desorption isotherms of **UTL** germanosilicate samples

Table S1: Textural properties of **UTL** germanosilicate samples determined by argon adsorption

Si/Ge (synthesis)	Si/Ge (product)	BET (m ² /g)	S _{external} (m ² /g)	V _{total} (cm ³ /g)	V _{micro} (cm ³ /g)
0.33	0.79	250	8.6	0.11	0.10
0.50	1.80	442	15	0.20	0.17
1.00	2.55	494	42	0.22	0.19
2.00	3.22	520	42	0.23	0.21
3.00	3.6	505	38	0.23	0.20
4.00	4.75	480	45	0.22	0.20
5.00	5.26	430	66	0.23	0.15
7.00	12.8	162	49	0.12	0.03

Figure S3: A) Schematic illustration of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{GeO}_2$ precipitation; B) correlation of the Si/Ge molar ratio in the synthesis gel and in the recovered bulk solid; C) correlation of the Si and Ge incorporation (%) with sample total pore volumes and micropore volumes.

Figure S4: a) powder XRD patterns of **UTL** samples (* = reflections of the product of re-crystallisation) and b) variation of crystal aspect ratios as a function of time.

Figure S5: SEM images of **UTL** zeolite samples recovered in different synthesis durations.

Figure S6: TEM images and electron diffraction of the **IWW** (Si/Ge = 4) crystal compared to the theoretical **IWW** topology and crystallographic axes